

ENERGIZE

An educational game about Positive Energy Districts

2030
NEUTRALPATH

Co-funded by
the European Union

“Energize” is an educational game where players learn about energy consumption, efficiency and sustainability. They can purchase products, organise awareness activities, and understand how individual habits affect the energy use of a neighbourhood.

Approach

Energize uses gamification to make complex topics—such as energy saving, building retrofitting, and electric mobility—easy to understand.

The game was developed within the European project NEUTRALPATH, which supports cities on their path toward climate neutrality through citizen participation. Energize was created to engage people in this process and present the project in an appealing, interactive way.

How it works

Designed for 2 to 4 players, ages 8+, Energize challenges participants to transform a district by investing in products, services, and educational initiatives while learning about the impact of everyday actions.

The goal: be the first to achieve zero energy consumption in your district using four types of cards: Product, Education, Behaviour & Chance.

Availability

Energize is available in six languages: English, Spanish, French, Dutch, German and Turkish, , with French, Greek and Italian currently being implemented.

The game was co-created with five European living labs through the NEUTRALPATH project and has been showcased in different events as an educational tool to explore the future of energy.

Interested in playing?

Contact us: hello@threeoclock.co

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